

BEYOND ETHNIC OUTBIDDING: ELECTORAL DESIGN AND STRATEGIC ADAPTATIONS IN IRAQI KURDISTAN

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This study investigates how electoral system design shapes intra-ethnic competition, focusing on Iraqi Kurdistan from 1992 to 2013. Challenging Horowitz's outbidding model, which assumes that ethnic parties escalate demands to outcompete rivals, this research demonstrates that electoral rules—including thresholds, ballot structures, and district demographics—mediate party strategies. Through mixed-methods analysis of elections, party platforms, and campaign materials, the findings reveal that high thresholds incentivize coalition-building, while their absence enables narrower appeals. Similarly, heterogeneous districts encourage inclusive strategies targeting diverse electorates, while homogeneous districts promote exclusivist appeals. The study concludes with actionable recommendations for electoral system design to balance inclusivity, stability, and representation in divided societies.

Key words: electoral systems; intra-ethnic competition; thresholds; ballot structures; Kurdish politics; Iraqi Kurdistan; ethnic party strategies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Electoral systems profoundly shape political parties' strategies, goals, and interactions, particularly in multiethnic societies where electoral rules mediate both inter- and intra-ethnic competition (Lijphart 1994; Taagepera and Shugart 1989; Reilly 2001; Norris 2004). While research has extensively examined inter-ethnic competition under varying electoral systems (Horowitz 1985; Lijphart 1999), the mechanisms shaping intra-ethnic competition remain less explored (Tarkhani 2024; Bochsler 2007; Birnir 2007). This study addresses this gap by investigating how electoral thresholds, ballot structures, and district demographics shape intra-ethnic competition in Iraqi Kurdistan.

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Horowitz's (1985) seminal outbidding model posits that intra-ethnic competition compels parties to escalate demands to surpass rivals. However, this model overlooks the moderating influence of electoral systems. Institutional constraints, such as high thresholds, encourage broad-based coalitions, while permissive rules, like open-list systems, enable fragmented appeals (Chandra 2004; Norris 2004). This research contends that electoral design, rather than ethnic rivalry alone, determines whether parties adopt bridging or bonding strategies.

Iraqi Kurdistan provides a compelling case study. Since its first parliamentary elections in 1992, the region has experienced significant shifts in electoral frameworks, including changes in thresholds, ballot structures, and district demographics. Major parties such as the Kurdistan Democratic Party (KDP), the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan (PUK), the Gorran Movement, and the Kurdistan Islamic Union operate within a diverse demographic landscape that includes Kurds, Turkmen, Christians, and Yazidis. These parties' inclusion of minority communities in their electoral platforms is shaped by institutional incentives.

This study asks how do electoral system variables—thresholds, ballot structures, and district demographics—shape intra-ethnic party competition in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq? It further examines whether these institutional variables moderate the bonding vs. bridging strategies Kurdish parties adopt. For example, high thresholds historically fostered coalition-building, while semi-open-list systems enabled more fragmented campaigning (Carey and Shugart 1995; Hangartner 2019). Similarly, heterogeneous districts like Kirkuk incentivize inclusive rhetoric, while homogeneous regions such as Duhok encourage bonding appeals (Reilly 2001; Norris 2004). This study challenges conventional models of ethnic outbidding by demonstrating that electoral rules moderate party strategies, offering both theoretical and empirical insights into intra-ethnic dynamics.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The relationship between electoral systems and party behaviour remains central to political science research, particularly in divided societies. Electoral rules shape party strategies, influencing coalition-building, ideological positioning, and voter outreach (Lijphart 1994; Taagepera and Shugart 1989). Proportional representation (PR) systems, for instance, promote inclusivity and minority representation, but their effects depend on electoral thresholds. High thresholds incentivize coalition-building by limiting party fragmentation, whereas low thresholds enable smaller parties to pursue particularistic appeals (Bochsler 2007; Norris 2004).

While extensive research has examined inter-ethnic party competition (Horowitz 1985; Lijphart 2004), the study of intra-ethnic dynamics remains underdeveloped. Horowitz's outbidding model suggests that ethnic parties escalate demands to outflank rivals, yet this framework often overlooks the moderating effects of institutional constraints (Chandra 2004). Recent studies challenge this model by demonstrating how high thresholds and structured ballot systems reduce radicalization by fostering coalition-building and cross-ethnic cooperation (Reilly 2001; Lubin 2017).

Bochsler (2007) and Birnir (2007) highlight how intra-ethnic competition in permissive systems leads to fragmented party landscapes, particularly in

homogeneous regions. In contrast, structured electoral designs—through thresholds and ballot centralization—moderate exclusivist appeals by compelling parties to expand their voter base (Zuber 2015). This study builds on these insights to examine how electoral thresholds, ballot structures, and district composition jointly shape intra-ethnic competition in Iraqi Kurdistan.

To conceptualize party strategies, the study adopts the bridging-bonding framework (Norris 2004; Reilly 2001). Bridging strategies, which emphasize cross-ethnic cooperation, are typically incentivized by high thresholds or heterogeneous districts. For instance, Kurdish parties in Kirkuk have historically emphasized regional development and shared governance to attract diverse voters (Rudaw 2019). In contrast, bonding strategies focus on consolidating support within a core ethnic base, often prevalent in homogeneous districts or low-threshold environments. The PUK's nationalist rhetoric in Sulaymaniyah during the 2014 elections exemplifies such bonding appeals (PUK Media 2014).

Despite advances in the field, existing research has yet to fully explain how electoral design interacts with district composition to shape intra-ethnic competition. While most studies focus on inter-ethnic competition (Horowitz 1985; Chandra 2004), the role of institutional constraints in moderating exclusivist appeals remains underexplored. By analysing electoral thresholds, ballot structures, and district heterogeneity, this study provides new insights into how institutional design influences Kurdish party strategies, contributing to broader debates on party competition in divided societies.

3 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study examines how electoral design and district composition shape intra-ethnic party competition, challenging Horowitz's (1985, 141) outbidding model, which posits that ethnic parties escalate demands to outcompete rivals within their ethnic group. While influential, this model overlooks the moderating effects of institutional constraints, such as electoral thresholds, ballot structures, and district demographics, which collectively influence whether parties adopt bridging or bonding strategies (Chandra 2004, 20–21; Norris 2004, 89). By integrating insights from ethnic party competition, electoral system design, and district-level dynamics, this study develops a framework that emphasizes the interaction of institutional and contextual factors in shaping party behaviour.

Horowitz's (1985, 142–144) outbidding model assumes that ethnic identities are fixed and that intra-ethnic competition inevitably leads to the escalation of radical demands. However, this perspective neglects the role of institutional mechanisms that can moderate these tendencies. For example, high electoral thresholds compel parties to aggregate votes from diverse constituencies, promoting inclusive coalition-building. Similarly, ballot structures that centralize candidate selection encourage parties to prioritize collective goals over narrow appeals, reducing incentives for outbidding (Chandra 2004, 22–23; Norris 2004, 90). Building on critiques by Chandra (2004, 24) and Zuber (2015, 518–520), this study contends that intra-ethnic competition is shaped not solely by ethnic rivalry but also by institutional constraints and contextual pressures, particularly district composition.

Recent contributions to the study of ethnic party strategies (Norris 2004, 91–93; Zuber 2015, 519) highlight two primary strategies: bridging and bonding. Bridging strategies are inclusive appeals aimed at cross-ethnic cooperation and

are typically driven by heterogeneous districts or high electoral thresholds that require broad-based voter support. For example, in Kirkuk, Kurdish parties formed alliances such as the Brotherhood and Coexistence Alliance to attract Arab and Turkmen voters, demonstrating the influence of district diversity on inclusive rhetoric (Rudaw 2019, 12; McDowall 2007, 321). Conversely, bonding strategies are exclusive appeals targeting a core ethnic base, often encouraged by homogeneous districts or low thresholds that lower the barriers to entry for narrowly focused parties. For instance, in Sulaymaniyah, the PUK's 2014 platform intensified ethnic demands to counter Gorran's urban reformist appeal, contrasting with the party's more inclusive rhetoric in Kirkuk (KNN 2013, 5–6; PUK Media 2014, 27). These strategies are not fixed but vary in response to institutional incentives and contextual pressures, such as district composition. Moreover, the interaction of electoral system variables—such as thresholds in heterogeneous districts or ballot structures in homogeneous areas—can amplify or mitigate these strategic choices (Reilly 2001, 65–67). Bridging strategies refer to inclusive appeals aimed at cross-ethnic cooperation—e.g., multilingual campaigns, interethnic electoral coalitions, or shared governance platforms. Bonding strategies emphasize ethnic identity, exclusivist narratives, or ideological particularism, typically resonating within a homogeneous constituency. While not inherently radical, bonding strategies tend to reduce cross-ethnic coalition potential.

Three key institutional variables shape ethnic party strategies: electoral thresholds, ballot structures, and district composition. High electoral thresholds act as filters, compelling parties to aggregate votes across diverse constituencies to secure representation, thereby reducing the viability of narrowly focused parties (Farrell 2011, 112). For example, the high 7% threshold in the 1992 Kurdistan elections forced the KDP and PUK to adopt bridging strategies focused on pragmatic goals such as security and stability (McDowall 2007, 323). In contrast, the removal of thresholds in the 2005 and 2009 elections enabled smaller parties, such as the Kurdistan Islamic Group and Kurdistan Islamic Union, to pursue bonding strategies with narrower Islamic/ideological appeals to Islamists who had traditionally voted to their Islamic parties (Al Baziani 2006, 243). In practice, KIG aligned with other Islamist factions rather than broad multi-ethnic coalitions. For instance, you could revise to: “the Kurdistan Islamic Group pursued bonding strategies by allying with fellow Islamist parties (e.g. the Kurdistan Islamic Union) and focusing on its conservative Kurdish support base (Romano 2006, 14; Baker 2014). Ballot structures further shape party strategies by influencing the degree of candidate centralization. Closed-list systems, which concentrate candidate selection within party leadership, promote party cohesion and coalition-building. By contrast, semi-open-list systems empower individual candidates, leading to personalized and fragmented campaigns. For example, the closed-list system in the 2005 and 2009 Kurdistan elections fostered broad coalitions, while the semi-open list introduced in 2013 encouraged localized appeals (Carey and Shugart 1995, 423; Hiltermann 2010, 19). District composition also plays a critical role: heterogeneous districts encourage bridging strategies that appeal to diverse electorates, while homogeneous districts incentivize bonding strategies that consolidate support within a core ethnic base. In Kirkuk, Kurdish parties adopted inclusive rhetoric to attract Arab and Turkmen voters, whereas in Duhok, the KDP's reliance on Kurdish nationalism and autonomy resonated with rural Kurdish constituencies (Reilly 2001, 68; Norris 2004, 94).

The interaction between these institutional variables and district composition further shapes party strategies. For example, high thresholds imposed by heterogeneous nature of districts reinforce bridging strategies by compelling

parties to seek cross-ethnic support. Kurdish parties in Kirkuk have emphasized regional development and shared governance to attract Turkmen and Arab voters (Rudaw 2019). Conversely, in homogeneous districts, high thresholds may encourage bonding strategies by limiting the viability of smaller, cross-cutting parties (Farrell 2011, 114). Similarly, semi-open-list systems in heterogeneous districts fragment bridging coalitions, while closed lists in such contexts foster cross-ethnic alliances by centralizing candidate selection (Carey and Shugart 1995, 424). These interactions are evident in Kurdish politics: Kirkuk's heterogeneous electorate required cross-ethnic coalition-building under the high threshold in 1992, while Sulaymaniyah's homogeneity facilitated exclusivist appeals after the removal of thresholds in 2005 (McDowall 2007, 324; Rudaw 2019, 13). Thus, electoral design, rather than ethnic rivalry alone, determines whether parties adopt bridging or bonding strategies, underscoring the importance of institutional context in shaping intra-ethnic competition.

This theoretical framework advances the study of ethnic party competition by demonstrating that electoral rules and district composition jointly shape party strategies. By showing that institutional constraints moderate the effects of intra-ethnic competition, the framework challenges the assumption that ethnic rivalry inevitably leads to radical demands. The interaction of electoral thresholds, ballot structures, and district demographics determines whether parties adopt bridging or bonding strategies, offering a more nuanced understanding of political behaviour in divided societies. This framework thus provides a foundation for examining how electoral design can promote inclusive governance and mitigate ethnic polarization in multiethnic contexts.

4 ANALYTICAL APPROACH: METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

This study employs a dual-method approach, combining process-tracing and qualitative content analysis to examine how electoral rules and district composition shape Kurdish party strategies. This mixed-method design facilitates causal inference and allows for a systematic analysis of party rhetoric, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of institutional and contextual influences.

Process-tracing establishes causal links by analysing sequences of institutional changes and their effects on party strategies. This method is particularly suited to examining the interaction between electoral thresholds, ballot structures, and district composition (George and Bennett 2005, 215). The study applies process-tracing to determine whether shifts from bridging to bonding strategies correspond with changes in electoral rules. For example, the removal of high thresholds in 2005 lowered barriers for smaller parties, enabling bonding strategies such as Komal's religious appeals (McDowall 2007, 314–316; Wimmer 2013, 127; KNN 2009). Similarly, the introduction of a semi-open-list system in 2013 encouraged personalized campaigns, as evidenced by the PUK's localized appeals in Sulaymaniyah (PUK Media 2014, 23–24). Comparative analysis across districts further isolates the effects of institutional variables. While Kirkuk's demographic diversity incentivized cross-ethnic coalition-building, Duhok's homogeneity fostered bonding strategies centred on Kurdish nationalism (Helbijardin 2013, 67; Rudaw 2019, 12). To strengthen causal inference, the study triangulates electoral data, campaign materials, and secondary literature (Lijphart 1999, 45–47; McDowall 2007, 318–320; Wimmer 2013, 129), ensuring that alternative explanations, such as economic grievances or external pressures from Baghdad, are accounted for.

While this study primarily focuses on Kurdistan Region parliamentary elections (1992–2013), it also draws on Kurdish party strategies in federal and provincial elections in districts like Kirkuk and Mosul. These areas lie outside the administrative boundary of the Kurdistan Region but offer insights into party adaptation in heterogeneous electoral contexts.

In addition to process-tracing, qualitative content analysis identifies thematic patterns in party rhetoric, enabling systematic comparisons across elections and districts. The analysis draws on a broad collection of political documents, including electoral manifestos, speeches, and campaign materials from major Kurdish parties (KDP, PUK, Gorran, and Komal). These sources were obtained from party archives, independent media outlets (such as Rudaw and KNN), and official electoral commission reports, ensuring a diverse range of perspectives. Materials were analysed in Kurdish, Arabic, and English to provide a comprehensive assessment of party rhetoric.

The coding process followed a structured framework to classify party rhetoric into two primary themes: bridging strategies, which emphasize cross-ethnic cooperation and inclusive governance, and bonding strategies, which focus on ethnic identity and exclusivist appeals. To enhance reliability, materials were collected from both party-affiliated and independent sources. Comparative analysis across heterogeneous and homogeneous districts further contextualized strategic variations, demonstrating how institutional and demographic factors influence party rhetoric.

By integrating process-tracing with qualitative content analysis, this study ensures a robust examination of Kurdish electoral politics. Process-tracing establishes temporal sequences linking institutional changes to shifts in party strategies, while content analysis provides a detailed examination of rhetorical patterns. Triangulation with secondary sources, including electoral commission data and scholarly analyses, strengthens the validity of the findings and mitigates potential biases.

5 ANALYTICAL APPROACH: EMPIRICAL INSIGHTS

This study employs a descriptive analytical approach to examine the strategic adaptations of Kurdish political parties under varying electoral systems and district compositions. By analysing electoral results, party platforms, and campaign materials, the research identifies patterns in party behaviour, particularly in the balance between bridging and bonding strategies, coalition-building and fragmentation, and the increasing personalisation of campaigns. The findings demonstrate that electoral thresholds, ballot structures, and district demographics are central factors in shaping intra-ethnic competition.

Electoral thresholds play a critical role in shaping party strategies by regulating inclusivity in political competition. High thresholds compel parties to aggregate votes across diverse constituencies, encouraging coalition-building and broad-based appeals. The seven percent threshold in the 1992 Kurdish parliamentary elections, for example, required dominant parties such as the Kurdistan Democratic Party and the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan to consolidate support across subethnic and regional lines. By contrast, smaller parties that relied on narrower bonding strategies, such as the Kurdistan Socialist Party, struggled to meet this threshold and failed to secure representation. However, the removal of

electoral thresholds in the 2005 and 2009 elections facilitated the emergence of smaller parties, including the Kurdistan Islamic Group and the Gorran Movement, both of which employed bonding strategies to target specific ideological or regional constituencies. This shift demonstrates how electoral rules shape the fragmentation of party competition over time.

Similarly, ballot structures influence intra-party dynamics and coalition stability. The transition from closed-list proportional representation in 2005 and 2009 to a semi-open-list system in 2013 altered electoral incentives, reshaping both party cohesion and candidate behaviour. Closed-list systems concentrated candidate selection within party leadership, strengthening ideological coherence and party unity. This system enabled the formation of broad electoral coalitions, such as the Democratic Patriotic Alliance of Kurdistan, which campaigned on shared goals such as regional autonomy and national security. The introduction of a semi-open-list system in 2013, however, allowed individual candidates greater autonomy, fostering personalised campaign appeals at the expense of party cohesion. This was particularly evident within the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan in Sulaymaniyah, where candidates adopted locally focused platforms, emphasising governance issues such as public services and anti-corruption rather than adhering strictly to nationalist rhetoric.

Beyond institutional constraints, district composition mediates the trade-off between inclusivity and exclusivity in party strategies. In Kirkuk, a multiethnic electoral district, Kurdish parties such as the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan moderated their rhetoric and pursued alliances with Turkmen and Arab voters, forming electoral coalitions such as the Brotherhood and Coexistence Alliance. These alliances emphasised inclusive governance, appealing to voters across ethnic and sectarian divides. In contrast, in homogeneous Kurdish provinces such as Sulaymaniyah and Duhok, parties relied on bonding strategies, appealing primarily to core Kurdish constituencies. The Kurdistan Democratic Party, for example, capitalised on tribal networks and nationalist sentiment, reinforcing its electoral stronghold in rural areas, whereas Gorran's success in Sulaymaniyah was driven by urban discontent with the dominance of the Kurdistan Democratic Party and the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan, as well as a strong emphasis on local governance and anti-corruption measures.

To ensure the validity and reliability of findings, the study employs methodological triangulation, integrating quantitative electoral data with qualitative content analysis of party materials and secondary sources. Electoral records from the Independent High Elections and Referendum Commission and the Kurdish Institute for Elections provide a statistical foundation for evaluating vote shares and seat distributions. Meanwhile, qualitative analysis of party manifestos, candidate speeches, and media coverage contextualises shifts in party rhetoric, demonstrating how institutional incentives shape electoral strategies over time.

By focusing on electoral design and intra-ethnic competition in Iraqi Kurdistan, this study contributes to the broader understanding of political behaviour in divided societies. It highlights the extent to which electoral rules moderate competition, shaping whether parties adopt inclusive or exclusionary campaign strategies. The findings underscore the importance of considering district-level demographic factors alongside institutional incentives, providing insights that may inform electoral reforms in similar post-conflict settings.

6 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section presents the study's empirical findings, demonstrating how electoral thresholds, ballot structures, and district composition have shaped Kurdish party strategies. The analysis examines whether high thresholds incentivise coalition-building and broad-based strategies, whether low thresholds encourage more fragmented, bonding-oriented appeals, and how ballot structures affect party cohesion and candidate personalisation. The findings also assess how heterogeneous districts foster cross-ethnic coalition-building, while homogeneous districts promote exclusivist strategies.

6.1 Electoral Thresholds and Party Strategies

The experience of Kurdistan Region Parliamentary elections between 1992 and 2009 illustrates the influence of electoral thresholds on party strategies, representation, and political dynamics. The 1992 elections, conducted under a proportional representation system with a seven percent electoral threshold, highlight how institutional mechanisms shaped coalition-building and moderated exclusivist appeals. To illustrate the range of elections under analysis, table 1 summarizes key institutional features of each.

TABLE 1: INSTITUTIONAL FEATURES OF ELECTIONS EXAMINED IN THE STUDY

Year	Election Type	District	Threshold	Ballot Type
1992	KRI Parliament	KRI-wide	7%	Closed-list PR
2005	KRI Parliament	KRI-wide	None	Closed-list PR
2009	KRI Parliament	KRI-wide	None	Closed-list PR
2013	KRI Parliament	KRI-wide	None	Semi-open list PR

The Kurdistan Democratic Party and the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan, the two dominant parties, adopted broad-based strategies to consolidate support across different subethnic and regional groups. The Kurdistan Democratic Party, for example, emphasised regional autonomy, economic development, and political stability, attracting support from tribal leaders and rural communities in Duhok and Erbil (McDowall 2007, 323). The Patriotic Union of Kurdistan combined Kurdish nationalism with a more inclusive appeal, integrating minority communities into its broader coalition, particularly in multiethnic regions such as Kirkuk (Leezenberg and Muller 1992, 58; Ahmad 2011, 112).

TABLE 2: ELECTORAL OUTCOMES IN THE 1992 IRAQI KURDISTAN PARLIAMENTARY ELECTIONS

Electoral Alliance	Votes	%	Seats	Leader
Kurdistan Democratic Party	437,879	45.3	51	Masoud Barzani
Patriotic Union of Kurdistan	423,833	43.8	49	Jalal Talabani
Islamic Movement of Kurdistan	49,108	5.1	0	Osman Abdulaziz
Kurdistan Socialist Democratic Party	24,882	2.6	0	Mahmoud Othman
Iraqi Communist Party	21,123	2.2	0	Aziz Muhammad
Kurdistan Popular Democratic Party	9,903	1.0	0	—
Independent Democrats	501	—	0	—

Source: Adapted from electoral commission reports and secondary sources (Habeeb 1998).

The threshold acted as a major barrier for smaller parties with more narrowly defined agendas. The Islamic Movement of Kurdistan, which campaigned on an Islamic governance platform, struggled to attract secular and moderate voters, receiving just over five percent of the vote and failing to meet the threshold for

representation. Similarly, the Kurdish Socialist Party's nationalist platform was unable to generate broad-based support, leading to its electoral failure (Stansfield 2003, 211; Habeeb 1998, 147). These results demonstrate how high thresholds discourage fragmentation by preventing the success of narrowly focused parties.

The removal of the threshold in the 2005 and 2009 elections significantly altered these dynamics. Without restrictive barriers, smaller parties were able to enter the political arena and appeal to more narrowly defined constituencies. The Kurdistan Islamic Group secured parliamentary representation in 2005 by focusing on religious values and appealing to rural and conservative voters disillusioned with the dominant secular parties (Bakawan 2017, 109; PeyamTV 2009, 4). Similarly, the emergence of the Gorran Movement in 2009 marked a shift towards more localised, reform-driven politics. Gorran capitalised on dissatisfaction with the ruling parties by focusing on anti-corruption and governance reform, particularly in Sulaymaniyah (Romano 2010, 145; KNN 2009, 5).

TABLE 3: 2005 KURDISTAN REGION PARLIAMENTARY ELECTION RESULTS

Electoral Alliance	Votes	%	Seats	Leader
Democratic Patriotic Alliance of Kurdistan	1,570,663	89.55	104	Jalal Talabani, Masoud Barzani
Kurdistan Islamic Group	85,237	4.86	6	Ali Bapir
Kurdistan Toilers Party and Independents	20,585	1.17	1	Qadir Aziz
Kurdistan Democratic Labour Party	11,748	0.67	0	—
Kurdistan People's Democratic Movement	10,953	0.62	0	—

Source: Kurdistan National Assembly, 2005 Election Data.

TABLE 4: 2009 KURDISTAN REGION PARLIAMENTARY ELECTION RESULTS

Political Entity	Votes	%	Seats
Kurdistani List (KDP & PUK)	1,076,370	57.34	59
Change List (Gorran)	445,024	23.75	25
Reform and Service List	240,842	12.8	13
Kurdistan Islamic Movement	27,147	1.45	2
Turkmen Democratic Movement	18,464	0.99	3

Source: Independent High Elections and Referendum Commission, 2009 Election Data.

These findings highlight the trade-offs associated with lower thresholds. While reducing barriers increased political diversity, it also led to greater political fragmentation, complicating coalition-building and governance. The Kurdish political landscape became increasingly competitive, with smaller parties challenging the Kurdistan Democratic Party and the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan's dominance. However, the absence of a threshold also encouraged more ideologically narrow strategies, as parties could prioritise core supporters over broad-based appeals (Reilly 2001, 67; Bochsler 2012, 94).

Ballot structures also played a crucial role in shaping party strategies. The transition from a closed-list proportional representation system in 2005 and 2009 to a semi-open-list system in 2013 altered intra-party dynamics by shifting incentives from party-driven to candidate-driven campaigning. In closed-list systems, party leadership-controlled candidate selection, ensuring ideological coherence and fostering coalition-building. This system encouraged broad electoral alliances, such as the Democratic Patriotic Alliance of Kurdistan, which promoted Kurdish autonomy and political stability as its primary objectives (Carey and Shugart 1995, 423; Bochsler 2007, 102).

The introduction of a semi-open-list system in 2013 allowed voters greater influence over candidate selection, leading to more individualised and localised campaigns. This change was particularly evident within the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan in Sulaymaniyah, where candidates focused on governance issues such as public services and anti-corruption rather than prioritising broader nationalist objectives (Hangartner 2019, 211; PUK Media 2013, 24).

District composition also shaped electoral competition. In multiethnic provinces such as Kirkuk, Kurdish parties moderated their rhetoric and pursued alliances with Turkmen and Arab voters to broaden their electoral appeal. The Patriotic Union of Kurdistan's participation in the Brotherhood and Coexistence Alliance illustrated how parties adjusted their strategies to attract diverse constituencies. By contrast, in more homogeneous Kurdish provinces such as Sulaymaniyah and Duhok, parties relied on bonding strategies that reinforced ethnic solidarity (McDowall 2007, 321; Wimmer 2013, 129).

These findings demonstrate the complex relationship between electoral thresholds, ballot structures, and district composition. High electoral thresholds encouraged broad-based strategies, while their removal fostered fragmentation. Changes in ballot structures influenced party cohesion, and district composition determined whether parties pursued inclusive, or exclusivist appeals. These dynamics illustrate how electoral design moderates' intra-ethnic competition, shaping party strategies in Kurdish politics.

6.2 Ballot Structures and Party Cohesion

The transition from closed-list systems in 2005 and 2009 to a semi-open-list system in 2013 reshaped intra-party dynamics and campaign strategies. Closed-list systems, which centralise candidate selection within party leadership, promote ideological coherence and coalition-building. Under this system, party elites control candidate placement on the list, ensuring alignment with broader party strategies. The Democratic Patriotic Alliance of Kurdistan, for example, united the Kurdistan Democratic Party and the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan under a platform focused on Kurdish autonomy and regional stability, minimising internal fragmentation and consolidating voter support (Carey and Shugart 1995, 423; Bochsler 2007, 102). The emphasis on party discipline in this system facilitated coalition-building and broad-based electoral appeals.

The introduction of a semi-open-list system in 2013 allowed voters to influence candidate selection, leading to greater personalisation of campaigns and a weakening of party cohesion. This shift was particularly evident within the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan in Sulaymaniyah, where candidates increasingly focused on locally relevant issues such as public services and anti-corruption, rather than adhering to a unified party narrative centred on Kurdish nationalism (Hangartner 2019, 211; PUK Media 2013, 24). As a result, intra-party competition intensified, with candidates prioritising personal electoral appeal over party cohesion.

The shift from a closed-list to a semi-open-list system also affected campaign strategies. Under the closed-list system, parties structured their electoral messaging around collective goals, such as security and regional governance, with party elites directing candidate priorities. By contrast, the semi-open-list system incentivised candidates to develop individual platforms, leading to a more fragmented electoral landscape. This transformation illustrates how ballot structures influence the balance between party-driven and candidate-driven strategies, with semi-open lists encouraging greater competition within parties

while reducing ideological unity.

6.3 District Composition and Strategic Variation

District demographics shape electoral strategies by determining the trade-offs between inclusivity and exclusivity. In Kirkuk, a multiethnic province, Kurdish parties moderated their rhetoric to appeal to Turkmen and Arab voters, forming alliances such as the Brotherhood and Coexistence Alliance (McDowall 2007, 321; Wimmer 2013, 129). These alliances emphasised cross-ethnic cooperation and inclusive governance, demonstrating the role of district heterogeneity in incentivising broad-based electoral strategies. The presence of multiple ethnic groups created electoral incentives for parties to adopt bridging strategies aimed at securing support across different communities.

By contrast, homogeneous provinces such as Sulaymaniyah and Duhok encouraged bonding strategies that reinforced ethnic solidarity and local grievances. In these provinces, electoral competition was predominantly intra-Kurdish, reducing the necessity for cross-ethnic coalition-building. The Kurdistan Democratic Party leveraged tribal networks and nationalist rhetoric to consolidate its core voter base, appealing to rural communities through promises of economic development and cultural preservation (Reilly 2001, 65; *Gulan Magazine* 2013, 8). Similarly, Gorran's success in Sulaymaniyah was rooted in its emphasis on local governance and anti-corruption, resonating with urban voters who had grown disillusioned with the long-standing dominance of the Kurdistan Democratic Party and the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan (Romano 2010, 145).

These patterns illustrate the extent to which district composition interacts with electoral design in shaping party strategies. In heterogeneous provinces, parties are incentivised to broaden their electoral appeals and form cross-ethnic alliances to maximise vote share. In homogeneous districts, where electoral competition occurs predominantly within a single ethnic group, parties rely on bonding strategies that emphasise ethnic identity, political grievances, and local concerns. The variation in party approaches across different districts underscores the importance of institutional and demographic factors in structuring intra-ethnic electoral competition.

6.4 District Composition and Party Strategies

The demographic and geographic composition of electoral districts in Iraqi Kurdistan has played a critical role in shaping party strategies and electoral outcomes. Heterogeneous provinces, such as Kirkuk and Mosul, incentivised bridging strategies that prioritised cross-ethnic collaboration, while homogeneous provinces, like Duhok and Sulaymaniyah, encouraged bonding strategies targeting core ethnic constituencies and localised appeals. These dynamics illustrate the interaction between district composition and electoral institutions, demonstrating how demographic diversity moderates the effects of electoral rules.

In heterogeneous provinces like Kirkuk, where Kurds, Arabs, Turkmen, and other minorities coexist, Kurdish parties adopted inclusive strategies to broaden their appeal beyond core Kurdish constituencies. The Patriotic Union of Kurdistan emphasised infrastructure development and coexistence, framing demands such as the implementation of Article 140 of the Iraqi Constitution as a regional benefit rather than an ethnic one (PUK Media 2014, 26). Campaign materials were produced in Kurdish, Arabic, and Turkish, underscoring this inclusive approach (Rudaw 2019, 12; McDowall 2007, 321). Similarly, the Kurdistan Democratic

Party employed coalition-building strategies, such as the Brotherhood and Coexistence Alliance during the 2013 Mosul provincial elections, to attract support from Turkmens, Christians, and other groups. This alliance secured 29.87 percent of the vote and 11 seats by emphasising shared goals such as security and economic development (IHEC 2013, 8).

TABLE 5: RESULTS OF THE 2013 PROVINCIAL ELECTION IN MOSUL PROVINCE

Electoral Entity	Votes	%	Seats
Brotherhood and Coexistence Alliance	173,687	29.87	11
Muttahidoon (Uniters for Reform)	129,556	22.28	8
Loyalty to Nineveh List	66,517	11.44	4
United Nineveh	45,971	7.91	3

Source: IHEC 2013, Provincial Election Data.

By contrast, homogeneous provinces like Duhok and Sulaymaniyah encouraged bonding strategies aimed at consolidating core Kurdish constituencies. In Duhok, the Kurdistan Democratic Party invoked Kurdish nationalism and leveraged tribal networks, emphasising its historical role as a defender of Kurdish identity and rights (Stansfield 2003, 210; Xebat 2014, 6). Meanwhile, in Sulaymaniyah, the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan and the reformist Gorran Movement competed intensely during the 2014 provincial elections. The Patriotic Union of Kurdistan adopted a nationalist platform centred on radical ethnic demands, including calls for a Kurdish confederation if Article 140 remained unimplemented. In contrast, Gorran focused on anti-corruption and economic grievances, resonating with urban voters frustrated by governance failures (Romano 2010, 145; PUK Media 2014, 27).

TABLE 6: RESULTS OF THE 2014 PROVINCIAL ELECTION IN SULAYMANIYAH PROVINCE

Party	Votes	%	Seats
Gorran Movement	359,600	39.66	12
Patriotic Union of Kurdistan (PUK)	318,723	35.15	11
Kurdistan Democratic Party (KDP)	88,655	9.57	3

Source: IHEC 2014, Provincial Election Data.

These findings illustrate how district heterogeneity fosters bridging strategies, while homogeneity enables bonding approaches that target specific constituencies. In more diverse electoral provinces, political parties must appeal to a broader constituency, incorporating cross-ethnic alliances to maximise electoral success. In contrast, homogeneous provinces reduce the incentive for coalition-building, enabling parties to prioritise ethnically driven or localised policy appeals.

However, the Kurdish case presents a more complex dynamic than traditional ethnic outbidding models suggest. Rather than consistently escalating ethnic demands, parties in homogeneous provinces often prioritised governance and socioeconomic reforms over radical nationalist rhetoric. The ability of parties to adapt their strategies to local electoral contexts reflects the moderating effects of institutional rules and voter preferences.

6.5 Interactions Between Institutions and District Composition

The interaction between electoral systems and district composition has profoundly shaped party strategies and electoral outcomes in Iraqi Kurdistan. Institutional design and demographic diversity have either amplified or constrained exclusivist appeals, depending on the electoral incentives present in each district. Heterogeneous provinces like Kirkuk incentivised bridging strategies aimed at cross-ethnic collaboration, while homogeneous provinces such as Duhok and Sulaymaniyah enabled bonding strategies that reinforced ethnic solidarity and localised concerns.

In Kirkuk, the multiethnic composition—comprising Kurds, Arabs, Turkmen, and others—created electoral pressures that discouraged reliance on ethnic-based appeals. Even in the absence of formal institutional barriers such as electoral thresholds, the necessity of attracting diverse voter blocs compelled dominant parties like the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan and the Kurdistan Democratic Party to adopt inclusive platforms. The Patriotic Union of Kurdistan framed policies such as the implementation of Article 140 of the Iraqi Constitution as broadly beneficial to all communities, rather than as an exclusively Kurdish demand. The Kurdistan Democratic Party, meanwhile, emphasised regional stability and coalition-building, as exemplified by the Brotherhood and Coexistence Alliance's success in the 2013 Mosul provincial elections (McDowall 2007, 322; Rudaw 2019, 13; IHEC 2013, 9). Smaller parties that lacked broad-based appeals, such as Komal and the Kurdistan Islamic Union, struggled to gain traction in diverse contexts (Ordeshook and Shvetsova 1994, 105).

Homogeneous provinces like Duhok allowed parties to adopt bonding strategies without significant electoral risk. The Kurdistan Democratic Party leveraged its deep organisational roots in the region, invoking Kurdish nationalism, tribal networks, and cultural identity to consolidate its voter base. This focus on ethnic solidarity was complemented by socioeconomic initiatives, such as rural development and infrastructure improvements, further solidifying the party's dominance (Stansfield 2003, 214; Norris 2004, 92). The district's homogeneity reduced the need for coalition-building, enabling the Kurdistan Democratic Party to maintain electoral dominance without moderating its rhetoric.

Sulaymaniyah presented a more complex dynamic due to its subethnic diversity and evolving institutional context. The introduction of a semi-open-list system in 2013 decentralised party control, allowing individual candidates to tailor their appeals to localised concerns rather than adhering to strict party discipline. This system amplified personalistic campaigns, as seen in the competition between the Patriotic Union of Kurdistan and Gorran. The Patriotic Union of Kurdistan emphasised historical achievements in Kurdish autonomy while addressing local grievances related to public services and rural development. Gorran, in contrast, capitalised on urban dissatisfaction by promoting anti-corruption measures and governance reform. This fragmentation weakened party cohesion, reflecting the trade-offs associated with decentralised electoral systems in homogeneous but politically competitive provinces (Goran.net 2019, 11; Taagepera and Shugart 1989, 221).

TABLE 7: ELECTORAL DYNAMICS BY DISTRICT IN IRAQI KURDISTAN

District	Key Parties	Strategy	Outcome
Kirkuk	KDP, PUK	Bridging: Multiethnic cooperation	Dominance of KDP/PUK coalitions
Duhok	KDP	Bonding: Kurdish nationalism, tribal ties	KDP landslide
Sulaymaniyah	PUK, Gorran	Localised appeals under semi-open lists	Gorran gains at PUK's expense

Source: Adapted from electoral commission reports, secondary sources (McDowall 2007; Habeeb 1998), and Rudaw (2019).

These patterns underscore the critical interplay between electoral rules and district demographics. High electoral thresholds in heterogeneous provinces, as observed in Kirkuk, mitigated polarisation by fostering cross-ethnic collaboration. In contrast, low thresholds and semi-open-list systems in homogeneous provinces, such as Sulaymaniyah, exacerbated political fragmentation by amplifying localised appeals. The Kurdish case also challenges conventional ethnic outbidding models, as even in homogeneous provinces, parties frequently prioritised governance and socioeconomic reforms over radical ethnic demands.

7 CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated how electoral design and district composition shape party strategies in divided societies, addressing key gaps in the literature on intra-ethnic competition. By analysing the interplay between institutional rules and demographic diversity, the research provides a deeper understanding of how party strategies evolve under varying electoral conditions. The findings underscore that high electoral thresholds and closed-list systems incentivise bridging strategies and promote ideological cohesion, particularly in heterogeneous provinces. Conversely, low thresholds and semi-open-list systems enable personalised and bonding-focused appeals, enhancing political representation but increasing party fragmentation.

The study also offers theoretical and practical insights into the role of electoral institutions in moderating ethnic competition. The findings challenge the applicability of Horowitz's (1985, 144–146) outbidding model, demonstrating that institutional constraints and voter preferences often prevent the escalation of radical ethnic appeals. Instead, electoral design moderates' intra-ethnic rivalry, promoting more inclusive political behaviour. These insights are particularly relevant for electoral policymakers considering how to balance representation with political stability in contested and multiethnic regions.

Despite its contributions, the study has certain limitations. It relied on publicly available election results and qualitative assessments of party strategies, which may not fully capture the complexities of voter behaviour or intra-party dynamics. Future research could integrate survey data, voter interviews, or experimental methods to provide a more detailed understanding of how electoral design influences political strategy. Additionally, while the study's findings offer valuable insights into electoral competition in Iraqi Kurdistan, further research is needed to explore whether similar mechanisms apply in other political settings.

By contextualising these findings within broader debates on electoral design, this study advances the understanding of intra-ethnic party competition and contributes to discussions on electoral reform in divided societies. Tailoring electoral systems to balance inclusivity and stability remains a critical challenge

in politically contested regions. Future research should further examine how these dynamics manifest across different electoral configurations, enhancing the understanding of political behaviour in ethnically diverse societies and informing electoral reforms aimed at fostering more inclusive governance.

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ONKRAJ ETNIČNEGA PRESEGANJA: VOLILNA ZASNOVA IN STRATEŠKE PRILAGODITVE V IRAŠKEM KURDISTANU

Članek analizira vpliv zasnove volilnega sistema na znotrajetnično politično konkurenco, s posebnim poudarkom na primeru iraškega Kurdistanu v obdobju 1992–2013. Študija izpodbija Horowitzov model »draženja«, ki predpostavlja, da etnične stranke stopnjujejo svoje zahteve z namenom prehiteti etnične tekmece. Nasprotno avtor ugotavlja, da so strategije političnih strank v večji meri oblikovane z volilnimi pravili – vključno z volilnimi pragovi, strukturo glasovnic in demografskimi značilnostmi volilnih okrožij. Z uporabo mešanih metod, ki vključujejo analizo volilnih rezultatov, programov političnih strank in kampanjskih gradiv, študija pokaže, da visoki volilni prag spodbuja oblikovanje predvolilnih koalicij, medtem ko njegova odsotnost omogoča polarizirane in partikularne nagovore volilcev. Podobno heterogena volilna okrožja spodbujajo vključujoče, široko usmerjene kampanje, medtem ko homogena okrožja krepijo ekskluzivistične, etnično usmerjene strategije. Študija se zaključi s praktičnimi priporočili za oblikovanje volilnih sistemov, ki naj bi v razdeljenih družbah uravnotežili cilje politične vključenosti, stabilnosti in reprezentativnosti.

Ključne besede: volilni sistemi; znotrajetnična konkurenca; volilni prag; glasovne strukture; kurdska politika; iraški Kurdistan; strategije etničnih strank.